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Molasses as A New Additive in Papermaking: for Bagasse and Kaolin Filled Bagasse pulps

By

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Figure 1

Sugarcane Bagasse is the fibrous plant residue left in the production of sugar after the cane has been pressed out.

Bagasse ranks among the renewable and sustainable raw materials.

Picture: Thamizhppanithi Maari

ABSTRACT

This work introduces, for the first time, molasses as a new additive for bagasse and kaolin filled bagasse pulps. It makes use of two most important byproducts of sugar industry (molasses and bagasse). Bagasse is also an important agricultural residue. Produced paper composites exhibited greater strength (breaking length) and remarkably higher water uptake (WRV) relative to molasses-free paper. Molasses succeeded to counteract deterioration in paper strength which occurs due to addition of inorganic fillers e.g. kaolin.

1. Introduction and Object:

Through previous work, the author introduced molasses -for the first time- as a new additive in papermaking. Molasses succeeded to strikingly improve the properties of paper made from the pulps investigated in the previous work i.e. cotton linters, wood pulp, & recycled old newsprint¹⁻⁴.

An important byproduct of the sugar extraction process is molasses. Final molasses is the liquid separated during centrifugation at the final step of processing sugarcane juice , when no further sugar may be extracted from the juice of sugarcane by conventional industry techniques. Sucrose present in molasses can not be extracted by economic methods. Sucrose lost in molasses represents the highest loss in sugar industry. The amount of sucrose lost, relative to the total sucrose can approach 9 % of sucrose present in sugarcane juice. Sucrose wasted in molasses is a serious problem, and a driving motive for the extensive research directed toward finding new innovative economic uses for this precious byproduct. The range of the amount of sucrose in molasses is 32–44 %. Reducing sugars are present in molasses, besides sucrose. These reducing sugars are glucose and fructose. The range of the amount of reducing sugars is 10 to 15 %. Therefore, the main importance of molasses, as an industrial byproduct, is the high value of fermentable sugars present in it. This value may reach 50

% by weight. Molasses, also, contains gums (including starch). The range of gums (including starch) is 3 to 5 % by weight⁵.

The present work aims at making use of the two most important byproducts of sugar industry; namely molasses and bagasse. Bagasse is also an important agricultural residue.

The present work introduces, for the first time, molasses as a new additive for bagasse and kaolin filled bagasse pulps.

2. Results and Discussions:

The bagasse pulp used in this work was taken non-dried from the industrial production line of an Egyptian pulp and paper factory in Upper Egypt. A part was air dried (A. D.), in sheet form. Physical and chemical analyses of this pulp was conducted by us. Table 1 shows the chemical and physical characteristics of this pulp. This commercial bleached bagasse pulp as provided in the non-dried state from the production line of the factory possessed very high water retention value (WRV) which amounted to 549 % and its °SR was 29.

2.1. Effect of Loading Bagasse Pulp with Molasses on Produced Paper Composites Properties

Molasses solutions of the concentrations 5, 10, 15 and 20 % w/w were used to impregnate the bagasse pulp. Pulp suspensions were processed into

paper sheets as mentioned in the experimental part. The obtained paper properties are shown in Table 2.

It is clear from Table 2 that loading bagasse pulp with various concentrations of molasses solutions, during preparation of stock and making of sheets, by suitable loading or incorporation techniques, resulted in improvements in the properties of the paper made therefrom. The loaded paper sheets water uptake (WRV) increased with increasing the concentration of the molasses solutions, reaching a maximum at loading molasses solution concentration of 20 % w/w. Dry breaking length of paper composites increased progressively. The wet breaking length also increased progressively.

Cell walls of cellulose fibers are natural nanoporous material. Sucrose and glucose molecules, present in molasses, are entrapped in this natural nanoporous structure, during its collapse, which happens when fibers are dried. Molecules of sucrose and glucose function as spacers. Thus, preventing the irreversible collapse of cell walls of cellulose fibers, during the drying process, at papermaking. Paper nanocomposites involving glucose and sucrose possess greater strength i.e. greater breaking length compared to normal cellulose fibers. This may be explained by assuming that sucrose and glucose molecules prevent the cell walls surrounding them from relaxation during drying. Thus, cell walls are strained, causing the partial release and protrusion of some microfibrils out of the fibers. These

protrusions cause more enmeshing of the fibers together during papermaking, and so the strength of the obtained nanocomposites increases. Thus, a new type of fibers beating occurs. In our previous research we called this type of beating, incorporation beating, to distinguish it from mechanical and chemical beatings, which are used traditionally to increase paper strength⁶⁻²⁹.

Moreover, the gums (including starch) present in molasses magnified the improvements in paper properties and acted as strength promoters¹⁻⁴.

2.2. Effect of Filling Bagasse Pulp with Kaolin, in Absence of Molasses

Properties of paper composites made from bagasse pulp filled with kaolin of increasing amounts (5, 10, 15 and 20 g of kaolin per 100 g of fibers) are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 illustrates that the strength (breaking length) of the paper composites, obtained from bagasse filled with kaolin, decreased by increasing kaolin added amounts. Strength of the kaolin-free paper (blank) was 5192 m, while that of the paper composites filled with kaolin decreased to 4 530 m, at adding 20 g of kaolin per 100 g of bagasse.

Also, the wet breaking length of paper composites decreased due to addition of kaolin. The wet breaking length of the blank (kaolin free paper) was 238 m, while that of the kaolin-filled paper composites decreased to 159 m, due to addition of 20 g of kaolin per 100 g of bagasse pulp.

Addition of inorganic fillers such as kaolin -normally- decreases the strength (breaking length) of the obtained paper composites. These fillers interrupt the inter-fiber bonding because they are located between the neighbouring cellulose fibers³⁰⁻³⁴.

2.3. Effect of Incorporating the Kaolin-Filled Bagasse Pulp with Molasses on the Properties of the Produced Paper Composites

Molasses solution of the concentration 10% w/w was used to load the non-dried kaolin-filled bagasse pulp. Non-dried kaolin filled molasses-incorporated bagasse pulp fibers were processed into paper sheet green nanocomposites as mentioned in the experimental part.

Table 4 shows properties of the green paper nanocomposites made from the molasses loaded kaolin-filled bagasse pulp, at increasing amounts of kaolin (5, 10, 15 and 20 g per 100 g) . Comparison of Table 3 and Table 4 shows clearly that the strength of green paper nanocomposites, produced from molasses-loaded kaolin-filled bagasse pulp, is greater than that of paper composites produced from the kaolin-filled molasses-free bagasse pulp. This was observed at all added amounts of kaolin.

The breaking length of paper composites made from kaolin-filled molasses-free bagasse was 4530 m, at adding of 20 g of kaolin per 100 g of bagasse pulp, while that of paper nanocomposites made from molasses-incorporated kaolin-filled bagasse was 5 389 m. It is evident from Table 4 that the green paper nanocomposites, produced from kaolin-filled bagasse

incorporated with molasses, acquired dry breaking length superior than that of the kaolin-free paper (blank). This achievement was true at all amounts of added kaolin.

Green paper nanocomposites, produced from kaolin-filled bagasse incorporated with molasses, acquired wet breaking length higher than that of paper composites produced from the kaolin-filled molasses-free bagasse pulp as illustrated through comparison of Table 3 and Table 4 . This is true for all the added amounts of kaolin. At adding 20 g of kaolin per 100 g of fibers, the wet breaking length, of the paper composites made from kaolin-filled bagasse in absence of molasses, was 159 m, in comparison to that of green paper nanocomposites made from kaolin-filled bagasse incorporated with molasses which was 401 m. Green paper nanocomposites, produced from kaolin-filled bagasse pulp incorporated with molasses, possessed wet breaking length superior than that of the blank (kaolin-free paper). This achievement was true at all the amounts of added kaolin, as shown by Table4.

It is clear from these results that the deterioration in strength of paper, normally occurring at adding inorganic fillers such as kaolin, was counteracted by incorporating bagasse pulp fibers, with molasses. Molecules of sucrose – in molasses – functioned as a strength promoter in the paper nanocomposites, produced from the molasses-incorporated kaolin-filled bagasse pulp fibers. The strength (breaking length) of these

paper nanocomposites, even, surpassed that of the blank (filler-free paper). Bagasse pulp, incorporated with molasses, was affected by incorporation beating. This increased the strength of the produced paper nanocomposites. The strength promoting effect of molasses was magnified by the gums and starch present in molasses.

3. Conclusions:

- ✓ The present work introduces, for the first time, molasses as a new additive for bagasse and kaolin filled bagasse pulps. The present work makes use of the two most important byproducts of sugar industry; namely molasses and bagasse. Bagasse is also an important agricultural residue.
- ✓ The paper composites involving bagasse and molasses, produced in this work, exhibit greater strength (breaking length) and remarkably higher water uptake (WRV) relative to molasses-free paper.
- ✓ Moreover, molasses succeeded in counteracting the deterioration in paper strength which usually occurs due to addition of inorganic fillers, such as kaolin.
- ✓ Sugar molecules present in molasses were manipulated, by simple fully green nanotechnology, to incorporate the natural nanoporous structure of the cellulose fibers involved in papermaking; thus increasing the water uptake and strength of paper, via incorporation beating. Whereas

the gums (including starch) -present in molasses- magnified these positive effects.

4. Experimental:

- Determination of centrifugal water retention value (WRV): -

Water retention values were determined according to the modified German Standard Method [35, 36].

- Loading of pulp fibers with molasses: -

In all experiments, the cellulosic fibers were incorporated with molasses solutions of the concentrations 5, 10, 15 and 20 %w/w^{1-4, 6-9, 11}.

- Paper Sheet Making: -

The paper sheets were prepared according to the SCA standard, using the SCA - model sheet former (AB Lorenzen and Wetter).

- The inorganic filler kaolin used in this work was Egyptian upgraded kaolin prepared on pilot scale, kindly provided by Metallurgical Research and Development Institute, El-Tebeen, Egypt. Its specifications and analyses are: Kaolinite 92.43% (Al_2O_3 35.21%, total SiO_2 44.43%, Fe_2O_3 0.92%, TiO_2 1.38%, moisture content 0.73%, ash content 87.99%, and brightness 73.90%). The bulk density of this kaolin was 0.846 before grinding and 1.1813 after grinding.

- Filling the cellulose fibers (bleached Egyptian bagasse pulp) with the conventional additive (inorganic filler kaolin): -

In all experiments, the cellulosic fibers (bagasse pulp) were mixed with kaolin and beaten for 15 minutes. The consistency was adjusted to 6%. The fibers were filled with increasing kaolin quantities (5, 10, 15 and 20g of kaolin per 100g of pulp fibers).

Investigations on different sorts of bagasse for pulp, paper and board manufacture are illustrated by example references^{31, 37-67}.

References

1. Fahmy TYA (2007) Introducing molasses as a new additive in papermaking. *Tappi Journal* 6(8):23
2. Fahmy TYA (2007) Molasses as a new Additive in papermaking: for high alpha-cellulose wood pulp. *Professional Papermaking* 4(1):42
3. Fahmy TYA, Mobarak F (2009) Advanced nano-based manipulations of molasses in the cellulose and paper discipline: Introducing a master cheap environmentally safe retention aid and strength promoter in papermaking. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 77(2):316
4. Fahmy TYA, Mobarak F (2014) Sustainability of Paper & Sugar Industries via Molasses: Novel Green Nanocomposites from Upgraded Recycled Cellulose Fibers. *Journal of American Science* 10(9):1
5. Barnes AC (1974) "The Sugar Cane", World Crop Series, Leonard Hill Books, London
6. Fahmy TYA, Mobarak F, Fahmy Y, Fadl MH, El-Sakhawy M (2006) Nanocomposites from natural cellulose fibers incorporated with sucrose. *Wood Science and Technology* 40(1):77-86
7. Fahmy TYA, Mobarak F (2008) Nanocomposites from Natural Cellulose Fibers Filled with Kaolin in Presence of Sucrose. *Carbohydrate Polymers* 72(4):751
8. Fahmy TYA, Mobarak F (2008) Vaccination of biological cellulose fibers with glucose: A gateway to novel nanocomposites. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 42(1):52
9. Fahmy TYA, Mobarak F (2011) Green Nanotechnology: A Short Cut to Beneficiation of Natural Fibers. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 48(1):134
10. Fahmy TYA, Mobarak F (2013) Advanced binderless board-like green nanocomposites from debarked cotton stalks and mechanism of self-bonding. *Cellulose* 20(3):1453
11. Fahmy TYA, Mobarak F, Fahmy Y (2016) Incorporation of Never-Dried Cotton fibers with Methylmethacrylate: A Gateway to Unique Transparent Board-Like Nanocomposites. *International Journal of ChemTech Research* 9(12):191-200
12. Fahmy Y, Mobarak F (1971) On fine structure of cellulose fibers. *Svensk Papperstidning* 74(1):2-9
13. Fahmy Y, Mobarak F (1971) Fine structure and reactivity of cellulose. *Journal of Polymer Science Part B Polymer Letters* 9(10):767-769
14. Fahmy Y, Mobarak F (1972) Fine structure of acetylated cellulose fibres. *Svensk Papperstidning* 75(21):853-8
15. Fahmy Y, Mobarak F (1972) Reactivity of biological cellulose and properties of some of its derivatives. *Cellulose Chemistry and Technology* 6(1):61-65
16. Fahmy Y, Mobarak F (1976) On the properties of never-dried and nature-dried cotton. *Cellulose Chemistry and Technology* 10(3):261-4
17. Fahmy Y, Abou-state M A (1961) Evaluation of rayon grade dissolving pulps. I. The influence of morphological, chemical, and certain physical properties of the pulps on the filterability of their viscose solutions. *Papier* 15:44-51
18. Fahmy Y, Abou-state M A (1961) Evaluation of rayon grade dissolving pulps. II. The influence of the average degree of polymerization and the zero-fiber fraction on the filterability of viscose. *Papier* 15:188-90

19. Fahmy Y, Abou-state M A, Roffael E (1961) Evaluation of rayon grade dissolving pulps. III. Pulps produced from reeds by various bisulfite and prehydrolysis sulfate procedures. *Papier* 15:666-71
20. Fahmy Y, Roffael E (1964) Evaluation of rayon grade dissolving pulps. IV. The influence of hydrolytic and oxidative degradation of cotton linters and wood pulps and their effects on the properties and filterability of viscose solutions. *Papier* 18(4):159-63
21. Fahmy Y, Nagati A (1965) Evaluation of rayon grade dissolving pulps. V. The classification of rayon grade pulps. *Papier* 19:570-72
22. Fahmy Y, Fadl M H (1964) On Emulsion xanthation of cellulose. I. Xanthation in the presence of sodium hydroxide and potassium hydroxide solutions. *Svensk Papperstidning* 67(3):101-9
23. Fahmy Y, Fadl M H (1964) On Emulsion xanthation of cellulose. II. Aspects of the reaction mechanism and acceleration of cellulose emulsion xanthation by inclusion or occlusion with CS₂ in fibers. *Svensk Papperstidning* 67(7):279-85
24. Fahmy Y, Mustafa A, Fadl M H (1964) On Emulsion xanthation of cellulose. III. Rate curves of included and nonincluded cellulose. *Svensk Papperstidning* 67(15):573-8
25. Fahmy Y, Fadl M H (1964) On Emulsion xanthation of cellulose. IV. Correlation between dissolution rate curves and technical viscose filterability 67(16):622-5
26. Fahmy Y, Fadl M H, Roffael E (1965) On emulsion xanthation of cellulose. V. Influence of some chemical and mechanical treatments on pulp reactivity and properties of viscose from included cellulose fibers. *Svensk Papperstidning* 68(16):549-52
27. Fahmy Y, Koura A (1967) On Fibrous acetylation of cellulose. I. Acetylation of cotton fibers. *Cellulose Chemistry and Technology* 1(3):301-12
28. Fahmy Y, Koura A (1969) On Fibrous acetylation of cellulose. II. Acetylation of viscose rayon. *Cellulose Chemistry and Technology* 3(2):179-87
29. Fahmy Y (1952) Zusammensetzung des Cellulose-Kobaltäthylendiamin-Komplexes: Diplomarbeit 106. Diss.
30. Casey JP (1962) "Pulp and Paper", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York
31. Fahmy Y, Fahmy TYA, Mobarak F, El-Sakhawy M, Fadl MH (2017) Agricultural Residues (Wastes) for Manufacture of Paper, Board, and Miscellaneous Products: Background Overview and Future Prospects. *International Journal of ChemTech Research* 10(2):424-448
32. Fahmy TYA, Abou-Zeid RE, Fahmy Y (2014) Response of pulps of different origins to the upgrading effect of bulk added green denatured soy protein, in correlation to morphological structure & chemical composition of cellulose fibers. *Nature and Science* 12(4):79-83
33. Mobarak F, El-Shinnawy NA, Soliman AAA (1998) Effect of some chemical treatments of upgraded Egyptian Kaolin on its retention by bagasse pulp. *Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research* 57 (6):316-323
34. Mobarak F, Augustin H (1976) Cationic starch in papers with high content of bagasse pulp.2. Influence on filler retention and properties of writing and printing papers. *Papier* 30 (3):100-102
35. Jayme G, Ghoneim AF, Krueger H (1958) Verbesserte Messung des Wasserrueckhaltevermoegens hochgemahlener Zellstoffe. *Papier* 12:90
36. Merkblatt IV/33/57/, Bestimmung von Zellstoffe Wasserrueckhaltevermoegens. Verein der Zellstoff und Papier Chemiker und Ingenieure.
37. Fahmy Y, El-Ashmawy A E (1958) A new method for production of viscose rayon pulp from bagasse. *Tappi* 41:439-42
38. Fahmy Y, El-Ashmawy A E (1959) Pulp and paper from sugar cane bagasse. *Indian pulp and paper* XIV(5):1-7
39. Fahmy Y, Fadl M H, Fadl N A (1969) Studies of pulping methods of bagasse for newsprint making. *Journal of Chemistry of The United Arab Republic* 12(2):219-27
40. Fahmy Y, El-Kalyoubi S (1970) Fibrous acetylation of cellulose. III. Acetylation of paper pulps. *Cellulose Chemistry and Technology* 4(6):613-19
41. Fahmy Y, Fadl N A (1974) A study of the production of hardboard from some indigenous agricultural residues. *Egyptian Journal of Chemistry* 17(3):293-301
42. Mobarak F, Augustin H (1976) Cationic starch in papers with high content of bagasse pulp. 2. Influence on filler retention and properties of writing and printing papers. *Papier* 30:100-102
43. Fahmy Y, Saleh T M, Hafez O M A (1972) On the Deleignification of rice straw and sugar cane bagasse. *Egyptian Journal of Chemistry* 15(6):591-599
44. El Shorbani S, Tawfik I, El Sadani M, Fahmy Y (1974) Preparation of viscose rayon pulp from sugar-cane bagasse. *Egyptian Journal of Chemistry* 17:255-65

45. El-Ashmawy A E, El-Kalyoubi S, Fahmy Y (1975) Hemicelluloses of bagasse and rice straw. *Egyptian Journal of Chemistry* 18:149-156
46. Mobarak F, Fahmy Y, Augustin H (1976) Cationic starch in papers with high content of bagasse pulp. 1. Influence on strength properties of kraft papers. *Papier* 30(1):16-19
47. Fadl M H, Hiekel S, Fahmy Y (1977) Bleachability of rice straw and bagasse paper pulps and their mixture. *Indian Pulp and Paper* 32(2):7-9
48. Mobarak F (1981) Bleaching of bagasse pulp by potassium permanganate. *Indian Pulp and Paper* 36(1):17-20
49. Mobarak F (1983) Polymerization of methyl methacrylate in water in presence of depithed bagasse and pith. *Acta Polymerica* 34(6):332-5
50. Mobarak F, Augustin H (1984) Composite hardboard from pith and depithed bagasse-filled plastics. *Research and Industry* 29(2):108-13
51. Mobarak F, Fahmy Y, Augustin H (1982) Binderless lignocellulose composite from bagasse and mechanism of self-bonding. *Holzforschung* 36(3): 131-136
52. Fahmy Y (1982) Pyrolysis of agricultural residues. I. Prospects of lignocellulose pyrolysis for producing chemicals and energy sources. *Cellulose chemistry and technology* 16(3): 347-55
53. Mobarak F, Fahmy Y, Schweers W (1982) Production of phenols and charcoal from bagasse by a rapid continuous pyrolysis process. *Wood Science and Technology* 16(1): 59-66
54. Mobarak F (1981) Bleaching of bagasse pulp by potassium permanganate. *Indian Pulp and Paper* 36(1):17-20
55. Mobarak F (1983) Polymerization of methyl methacrylate in water in presence of depithed bagasse and pith. *Acta Polymerica* 34(6):332-5
56. Mobarak F, Augustin H (1984) Composite hardboard from pith and depithed bagasse-filled plastics. *Research and Industry* 29(2):108-13
57. Fahmy Y, Ibrahim A, El-Sakhawy M (1994) Acetylation and carboxymethylation of wood, bagasse and rice straw pulps. *Research and Industry* 39(1):29-34
58. Nada A M, Fahmy Y, Elbaiuomy H (1994) Spectroscopic studies of bagasse butanol lignin. *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 46(3):295-302
59. El-Sakhawy M, Fahmy Y, Ibrahim A, Lönnberg B (1995) Organosolv pulping. I. Alcohol pulping of Bagasse. *Cellulose Chemistry and Technology* 29(5):615-629
60. El-Sakhawy M, Lönnberg B, Fahmy Y, Ibrahim A (1996) Organosolv pulping. 5. Bleachability and paper properties. *Cellulose Chemistry and Technology* 30(5-6):483-495
61. Nada A M, Ibrahim A, Fahmy Y, Abo-Yousef H E (1995) Bagasse pulping with butanol-water system. *Research and Industry* 40(3):224-30
62. Nada A M, Fahmy Y, El-Bayoumi H (1996) Bleaching of Egyptian bagasse pulps with CEH and CEOH sequences. *Journal of scientific and industrial research* 55(7):516-522
63. Nada A M, Fahmy Y, Abo-Yousef H E (1998) Kinetic study of delignification of bagasse with butanol - Water organosolv pulping process. *Journal of scientific and industrial research* 57(8):471-476
64. Nada A M, Ibrahim A, Fahmy Y, Abo-Yousef H E (1999) Peroxyacetic acid pulping of bagasse and characterization of the lignin and pulp. *Journal of scientific and industrial research* 58(8):620-628
65. Nada A M, Ibrahim A, Fahmy Y, Abo-Yousef H E (2002) Peroxyacetic acid pulping of bagasse. I. Two-stage pulping. *Cellulose Chemistry and Technology* 36(1):123-136
66. Fahmy Y, El-Wakil N A, El-Gendy A A, Abo-Zeid R E, Youssef M A (2010). Plant proteins as binders in cellulosic paper composites. *International journal of biological macromolecules* 47(1): 82-85
67. Fahmy T Y A, Mobarak F, Kassem N, Abdel-Kader A H (2008) New approach for upgrading pulp & paper quality: Mild potassium permanganate treatment of already bleached pulps. *Carbohydrate polymers* 74(4): 892-894

Table 1

Analysis and physical properties of the bleached bagasse pulp

Alphacellulose %	83.22
Pentosane %	14.84
Ash Content %	0.41
Lignin %	1.61
Water Retention Value (W.R.V.) A.D. %	238.91

Table 2

Properties of paper made from bagasse pulp before and after loading the pulp with Molasses

Concentrations of the molasses solutions % w/w	zero	5	10	15	20
Breaking length in meters	4480	4832	5192	5194	5198
Wet breaking length in meters	205	226	238	240	241
W.R.V. of paper sheets %	122.37	128.34	135.13	136.21	136.29

Table 3

Effect of filling the bagasse pulp with kaolin -in absence of molasses- on the properties of the produced paper composites

Amounts of the added kaolin (in grams per 100 grams of bagasse pulp)	zero	5	10	15	20
Breaking length in meters	5192	4905	4801	4611	4530
Wet breaking length in meters	238	197	183	168	159

Table 4

Effect of incorporating the kaolin-filled bagasse pulp with molasses on the properties of the produced advanced paper green nanocomposites

Amounts of the added kaolin (in grams per 100 grams of bagasse pulp)	zero	5	10	15	20
Breaking length in meters	5192	5430	5400	5393	5389
Wet breaking length in meters	238	419	413	405	401